

Synthesis and biological evaluation of substituted benzimidazoles

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Abstract : A novel series of 2-methyl benzimidazole and 2,6-dimethyl benzimidazole (3a-3h, 4a-4h and 5a-5b) were synthesized. These compounds were characterized by Infra red spectroscopy, Proton nuclear magnetic resonance, Mass spectral data and elemental analysis. The synthesized compounds were screened for their antimicrobial, analgesic and anti-inflammatory activity. Most of the compounds showed antimicrobial, analgesic and anti-inflammatory activity. Compound 3a, 4a, 5a showed good antibacterial and 4f, 4g showed good antifungal activity. Compound 4a showed highest analgesic while 3c showed highest anti-inflammatory activity. So, can be concluded that benzimidazole derivatives impact on chemists and biochemists for further search of analgesic and anti-inflammatory agents containing Mannich bases.

Keywords : Mannich base, benzimidazole derivatives, antimicrobial, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, Ciprofloxacin, Clotrimazole, Diclofenac sodium.

Introduction

Benzimidazole is a heterocyclic aromatic organic compound. This bicyclic compound consists of the fusion of benzene and imidazole. The most prominent benzimidazole compound in nature is *N*-ribosyl-dimethylbenzimidazole, which serves as an axial ligand for cobalt in vitamin B₁₂¹. In 1960s, a broad-spectrum group of drugs, known as benzimidazoles, were discovered with a big-bang having specific activity against the gastrointestinal helminths². Benzimidazoles possess a wide variety of activities like cysticidal³, glucokinase activator⁴, angiotensin II receptor antagonist⁵, antiprozoal⁶, anticonvulsant⁷, antidiabetic⁷, analgesic and anti-inflammatory⁸, antitumour⁹ and antitumour^{9,10}. The literature survey reveals that benzimidazole derivatives continually showing promising and encouraging results so far as their antimicrobial, analgesic and anti-inflammatory activity is concerned. Present work is taken consideration to explore the antimicrobial, analgesic and anti-inflammatory activity¹¹⁻¹⁶.

Experimental

The melting point of the products was determined by open capillary method and was uncorrected. Elemental analysis was performed on Perkin-Elmer 2400 C, H, N analyzer, results were within $\pm 0.4\%$ of the predicted values for all compound. IR spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu IR Affinity-1 FTIR spectrophotometer, using DRS 8000A accessory technique. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker DPX-300 MHz spectrometer in CDCl₃ using TMS as a standard with resonant frequency of 300 MHz. The Mass spectra were recorded on a Bruker Daltonics micrOTOF-Q II by using (ESI) method. All the chemical reagents used were of LR grade and procured from Qualikems, Spectrochem and Aldrich. All solvents were distilled and dried in the usual manner.

General procedure for the synthesis of substituted o-phenylenediamine dihydrochloride (1a and 1b) :

Required *o*-phenylenediamine (0.1 mol) was dissolved in 20 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid and 15 ml of water containing 0.7 g of tin(II) chloride, and the hot

solution was treated with 0.2 g of decolourising carbon. Then the solution was filtered and 35 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid was added to the hot colourless filtrate. The filtrate was cooled in a freezing mixture of ice and salt. The colourless crystals of the dihydrochloride were collected on a buchner funnel.

Synthesis of substituted 2-methyl benzimidazoles (2a and 2b) :

Compounds (**1a** and **1b**) (0.1 mol), 66 ml of water and 18 g (0.3 mol) of acetic acid were heated under reflux for 45 min. The reaction mixture was cooled and distinctly basified by the gradual addition of concentrated ammonia solution. The precipitated product was collected and recrystallized from ethanol.

General procedure for the synthesis of N-Mannich bases of benzimidazole (3a to 3h and 4a to 4h) :

2-Methyl benzimidazole and 2,6-dimethyl benzimidazole (0.1 mol) reacted with secondary amine (0.1 mol) by taking in a flat bottom flask containing 20 ml alcohol. Then formaldehyde (0.1 mol) and 0.1 ml of hydrochloric acid were added to the reaction mixture and stirred for 1 h. It was refluxed for 1 h and refrigerated overnight. Then the solvent was removed under reduced pressure to get the crystals of Mannich base. The product was filtered and recrystallized using alcohol^{17,18}.

Spectral data :

2-Methyl-1-(piperazin-1-ylmethyl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazole (3a) : White crystals, yield 72%, m.p. 123–125 °C, $R_f = 0.52$, IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3120.76 (N-H stretching), 3062.96 (Ar C-H stretching), 1460 (Aliphatic C-H stretching), 1271.09 (C-N stretching); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.227–7.695 (4H, m, Ar), 4.824 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-$), 2.508 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.365–2.582 (4H, t, $-\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$), 2.645–2.867 (4H, t, $-\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$), 2.048 (1H, s, N-H); MS (m/z) : M^+ 230.

4-((2-Methyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)methyl)morpholine (3b) : White crystals, yield 74%, m.p. 152–153 °C, $R_f = 0.37$, IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3062.96 (Ar C-H stretching), 1460.56 (Aliphatic C-H stretching), 1261.19 (C-N stretching), 1122 (C-O stretching); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.228–7.694 (4H, m, Ar), 4.807 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-$), 2.517 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.316–2.617 (4H, t, Ar), 3.547–3.762 (4H, t,

Ar); MS (m/z) : M^+ 231.

2-Methyl-1-(piperidin-1-ylmethyl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazole (3c) : Light yellow crystals, yield 74%, m.p. 135–138 °C, $R_f = 0.48$, IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3062.96 (Ar C-H stretching), 1485.47 (Aliphatic C-H stretching), 1271.09 (C-N stretching); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.225–7.767 (4H, m, Ar), 4.713 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-$), 2.706 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.409–2.681 (4H, t, $2-\text{CH}_2-$), 1.521–1.909 (4H, m, $2-\text{CH}_2-$); MS (m/z) : M^+ 229.

2-Methyl-1-((4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)methyl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazole (3d) : Light yellow crystal, yield 70%, m.p. 161–162 °C, $R_f = 0.56$, IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3064.89 (Ar C-H stretching), 1458.47 (Aliphatic C-H stretching), 1285.45 (C-N stretching); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.225–7.767 (4H, m, Ar), 4.805 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-$), 2.513 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.326–2.662 (8H, t, $4-\text{CH}_2$), 2.267 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$); MS (m/z) : M^+ 244.

1-((4-Ethylpiperazin-1-yl)methyl)-2-methyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazole (3e) : Cream crystal, yield 75%, m.p. 166–168 °C, $R_f = 0.50$, IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3061.86 (Ar C-H stretching), 1462.29 (Aliphatic C-H stretching), 1272.67 (C-N stretching); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.225–7.669 (4H, m, Ar), 4.805 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-$), 2.517 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.182–2.346 (8H, t, $4-\text{CH}_2$), 2.396–2.496 (2H, q, $-\text{CH}_2$); MS (m/z) : M^+ 258.

2-Methyl-1-(pyrrolidin-1-ylmethyl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazole (3f) : Yellow crystal, yield 72%, m.p. 157–158 °C, $R_f = 0.43$, IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3055.27 (Ar C-H stretching), 1485.19 (Aliphatic C-H stretching), 1251.67 (C-N stretching); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.223–7.796 (4H, m, Ar), 4.807 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-$), 2.517 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.501–2.728 (4H, t, $2-\text{CH}_2$), 1.678–1.991 (4H, m, $2-\text{CH}_2$); MS (m/z) : M^+ 215.

N-Ethyl-N-((2-methyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)methyl)ethanamine (3g) : White crystal, yield 76%, m.p. 122–124 °C, $R_f = 0.53$, IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3115.96 (Ar C-H stretching), 1450.47 (Aliphatic C-H stretching), 1271.09 (C-N stretching); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.225–7.623 (4H, m, Ar), 4.810 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-$), 2.517 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.491–2.778 (4H, q, $-\text{[CH}_2\text{]}_2$), 0.805–1.157 (6H, t, $-\text{[CH}_3\text{]}_2$); MS (m/z) : M^+ 193.

N-((2-Methyl-1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazol-1-yl)methyl)-*N*-phenylaniline (**3h**) : Yellow crystals, yield 72%, m.p. 165–167 °C, $R_f = 0.47$, IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3041.96 (Ar C-H stretching), 1450.47 (Aliphatic C-H stretching), 1271.09 (C-N stretching); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.220–7.743 (4H, m, Ar), 5.517 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-$), 2.517 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 6.664–7.225 (10H, m, Ar-H); MS (m/z) : M^+ 313.

2,6-Dimethyl-1-(piperazin-1-ylmethyl)-1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazole (**4a**) : Amorphous light pink, yield 68%, m.p. 178–180 °C, $R_f = 0.68$, IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3150.67 (N-H stretching), 3062.56 (Ar C-H stretching), 1440.43 (Aliphatic C-H stretching), 1271.09 (C-N stretching); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.017–7.613 (3H, m, Ar), 4.787 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-$), 2.341 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.517 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.176–2.327 (4H, t, $-\text{CH}_2$), 2.576–2.789 (4H, t, 2- CH_2), 1.987 (1H, s, N-H); MS (m/z) : M^+ 244.

4-((2,6-Dimethyl-1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazol-1-yl)methyl)-morpholine (**4b**) : Light pink crystals, yield 70%, m.p. 153–155 °C, $R_f = 0.55$, IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3052.56 (Ar C-H stretching), 1450.47 (Aliphatic C-H stretching), 1251.36 (C-N stretching), 1130.87 (C-O stretching); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.033–7.541 (3H, m, Ar), 4.713 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-$), 2.315 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.497 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.412–2.537 (4H, t, 2- CH_2), 2.327–2.407 (4H, t, $-\text{CH}_2$); MS (m/z) : M^+ 245.

2,6-Dimethyl-1-(piperidin-1-ylmethyl)-1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazole (**4c**) : Amorphous red, yield 73%, m.p. 170–171 °C, $R_f = 0.60$, IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3052.56 (Ar C-H stretching), 1440.47 (Aliphatic C-H stretching), 1280.29 (C-N stretching); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.048–7.546 (3H, m, Ar), 4.773 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-$), 2.336 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.492 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.374–2.486 (4H, t, 2- CH_2), 1.398–1.537 (4H, m, 2- CH_2); MS (m/z) : M^+ 243.

2,6-Dimethyl-1-((4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)methyl)-1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazole (**4d**) : Amorphous red, yield 74%, m.p. 158–160 °C, $R_f = 0.63$, IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3074.27 (Ar C-H stretching), 1450.19 (Aliphatic C-H stretching), 1241.34 (C-N stretching); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.048–7.546 (3H, m, Ar), 4.773 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-$), 2.336 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.502 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.121–2.457 (8H, t, 4- CH_2), 2.197 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$); MS (m/z) : M^+ 258.

1-((4-Ethylpiperazin-1-yl)methyl)-2,6-dimethyl-1*H*-

benzo[*d*]imidazole (**4e**) : Amorphous red, yield 78%, m.p. 132–134 °C, $R_f = 0.58$; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3052.56 (Ar C-H stretching), 1460.11 (Aliphatic C-H stretching), 1271.09 (C-N stretching); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.059–7.532 (3H, m, Ar), 4.773 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-$), 2.337 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.517 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.123–2.467 (8H, t, 4- CH_2), 2.223–2.483 (2H, q, $-\text{CH}_2$), 0.947–1.185 (3H, t, CH_3); MS (m/z) : M^+ 272.

2,6-Dimethyl-1-(pyrrolidin-1-ylmethyl)-1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazole (**4f**) : Red crystals, yield 74%, m.p. 138–140 °C, $R_f = 0.64$, IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3047.45 (Ar C-H stretching), 1450.47 (Aliphatic C-H stretching), 1271.09 (C-N stretching); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.048–7.544 (3H, m, Ar), 4.781 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-$), 2.336 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.512 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.332–2.510 (4H, t, 2- CH_2), 1.543–1.776 (4H, m, $-\text{CH}_2$); MS (m/z) : M^+ 229.

N-((2,6-Dimethyl-1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazol-1-yl)methyl)-*N*-ethylethanamine (**4g**) : Red crystals, yield 64%, m.p. 145–147 °C, $R_f = 0.46$, IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3052.56 (Ar C-H stretching), 1450.47 (Aliphatic C-H stretching), 1261.19 (C-N stretching); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.048–7.546 (3H, m, Ar), 4.773 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-$), 2.336 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.517 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.537–2.823 (4H, q, $-\text{[CH}_2\text{]}_2$), 0.947–1.297 (6H, t, $-\text{[CH}_3\text{]}_2$); MS (m/z) : M^+ 231.

N-((2,6-Dimethyl-1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazol-1-yl)methyl)-*N*-phenylaniline (**4h**) : Red crystals, yield 68%, m.p. 176–178 °C, $R_f = 0.48$, IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3082.46 (Ar C-H stretching), 1450.65 (Aliphatic C-H stretching), 1282.27 (C-N stretching); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.048–7.539 (3H, m, Ar), 4.821 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-$), 2.338 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.517 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 6.659–7.465 (10H, m, Ar-H); MS (m/z) : M^+ 327.

General procedure for the synthesis of substituted cyclopentyl benzimidazole : Substituted 2-methyl and 2,6-dimethyl benzimidazole (0.1 mol) and sodium hydroxide (0.1 mol) were dissolved in acetonitrile (40 ml). After 1 h stirring, cyclopentyl bromide (0.1 mol) was added and the mixture was heated under reflux until the TLC monitored the disappearance of the starting material. Then the reaction mixture was evaporated to dryness and the residue was purified by recrystallization with alcohol¹⁸ (Fig. 1).

Step I – Preparation of *o*-phenylenediamine dihydrochloride **1a** and **1b**.

Step II – Preparation of 2-methyl benzimidazoles **2a** and **2b**.

Step III – Preparation of *N*-Mannich bases **3a-3h** and **4a-4h**.

Step IV – Preparation of compound **5a** and **5b**.

Fig. 1. Scheme for the synthetic compounds.

Spectral data :

1-Cyclopentyl-2-methyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazole (5a) : White crystals, yield 80%, m.p. 158–160 °C, $R_f = 0.55$, IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3045.60 (Ar C-H stretching), 1485.19 (Aliphatic C-H stretching), 1280.09 (C-N stretching), 2987.74 (Cycloalk C-H stretching); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.223–7.621 (4H, m, Ar), 2.508 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 3.646–3.859 (1H, m, $-\text{CH}$), 1.784–2.124 (4H, m, 2- CH_2), 1.323–1.654 (4H, m, 2- CH_2); MS (m/z) : M^+ 200.

1-Cyclopentyl-2,6-dimethyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazole (5b) : Amorphous pink, yield 82%, m.p. 185–187 °C, $R_f = 0.65$, IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3072.56 (Ar C-H stretching), 1460.87 (Aliphatic C-H stretching), 1281.09 (C-N stretching), 2967.37 (Cycloalk C-H stretching); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.058–7.539 (3H, m, Ar), 2.337 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 2.516 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 3.643–3.812 (1H, m, $-\text{CH}$), 1.784–2.126 (4H, m, 2- CH_2), 1.320–1.657 (4H, m, 2- CH_2); MS (m/z) : M^+ 214.

Biological activity :

Antimicrobial activity :

All synthesized compounds were tested for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity against two Gram-positive (*Bacillus subtilis* [MTCC 121], *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* [MTCC 424]), two Gram-negative (*Escherichia coli* [MTCC 118], *Klebsiella pneumoniae* [MTCC 7028]) and antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* [MTCC 1637] and *Aspergillus tubingensis* [MTCC 2479]. Paper disc diffusion method was used for antimicrobial assay. All compounds and standard drug were dissolved in DMF, at a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The paper discs which were previously sterilized by dry heat, impregnated with the test compounds (100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, dimethyl formamide as solvent) were placed on the solidified medium. The plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h in case of antibacterial assay and for antifungal assay, the plates were incubated at 37 °C for 48 h. Zone of inhibition of each compound was measured compared to standard drug Ciprofloxacin for antibacterial and Clotrimazole for antifungal assay at a concentration 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

Analgesic activity :

Acetic acid induced writhing method-using wistar albino mice (n = 6) of either sex (25–30 g) were used for study of analgesic activity^{19,20}. Diclofenac sodium was used as standard drug at a dose level of 25 mg/kg b.w. for comparison. The control received only solvent (0.5% Carboxy methyl cellulose (CMC)) and test groups were usually administered orally 30 min prior to intraperitoneal administration of the writhing agent (0.6% v/v aqueous acetic acid – 1 mL/100 g) with compounds **3a-3h**, **4a-4h**, **5a-5b** at a dose of 100 mg/kg b.w. (suspended in 0.5% CMC). The number of writhes was recorded for each animal for 15 min. A writhe is indicated by a stretching of the abdomen with simultaneous stretching of at least one hind limb. The percentage protection was calculated by following formula for analgesic activity (Fig. 2).

$$\% \text{ Protection} = 100 - [(\text{experimental/control}) \times 100]$$

Fig. 2. Bar graph showing analgesic activity of **3c**, **3e**, **4a**, **4e** and of Diclofenac sodium in 15 min.

Anti-inflammatory activity :

Anti-inflammatory activity was determined by the carrageenan-induced paw oedema method in wistar rats of either sex by using plethysmography according to winter's method²¹. Diclofenac sodium was used as standard drug at a dose level of 25 mg/kg b.w. for comparison. The control received only solvent (0.5% CMC), the remaining groups were usually administered with compounds

3a-3h, 4a-4h, 5a-5b at a dose of 100 mg/kg b.w. A 1% w/v suspension of carrageenan was prepared freshly in normal saline solution (0.9%) and injected 0.1 ml into subplantar region of left hind paw 1 h after the oral administration of test compound. A mark was made on left paw at the ankle joint of each rodent. The paw volume of control, standard and test groups were measured before and 3 h after the administration of carrageenan by digital paw oedema meter up to the fixed mark made on left paws to ensure constant paw volume (Fig. 3). The percentage inhibition of oedema was calculated by using following formula :

$$\% \text{ Inhibition of oedema} = \frac{[(\text{control} - \text{test})/\text{control}] \times 100}{}$$

Fig. 3. Bar graph showing anti-inflammatory activity of **3c, 3d, 3f, 4c, 4d, 4f** and of Diclofenac sodium after 3 h.

Statistical analysis :

Statistical analysis was done by one way ANOVA using Dunnett's test. There was significant difference between control and test compounds with $p < 0.01$ for analgesic and $p < 0.001$ for anti-inflammatory activity.

Results and discussion

Chemistry :

o-Phenylenediamine was treated with concentrated hydrochloric acid in the presence of tin(II) chloride to

form *o*-phenylenediamine dihydrochloride **1**²². *o*-Phenylenediamine dihydrochloride was refluxed with acetic acid and then reaction mixture was basified with concentrated ammonia solution to get derivatives of 2-methyl benzimidazole **2a** and **2b**²². *N*-Mannich bases **3a-3h** and **4a-4h** were synthesized by compound containing active hydrogen (2-methyl benzimidazoles) and secondary amines in the presence of formaldehyde^{16,17}. Compound **5a** and **5b** were formed by reaction of 2-methyl benzimidazole **2a** and **2b** with cyclopentyl bromide in the presence of base¹⁸. Their physical properties are reported (Table 1).

Antimicrobial activity :

All novel synthesized compounds were screened for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity against two Gram-positive (*Bacillus subtilis* [MTCC 121], *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* [MTCC 424]), two Gram-negative (*Escherichia coli* [MTCC 118], *Klebsiella pneumoniae* [MTCC 7028]) and antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* [MTCC 1637] and *Aspergillus tubingensis* [MTCC 2479] by paper disc diffusion method. All synthesized compounds and standard drugs were dissolved in DMF to form 100 µg/mL concentrations. Some of the compounds showed good activity against Gram-positive, Gram-negative bacteria and fungus. 2-Methyl benzimidazole derivative containing piperazine ring (**3a**), cyclopentyl ring (**5a**) and 2,6-dimethyl benzimidazole derivative containing pyrrolidine ring (**4f**) showed good activity while 2-methyl benzimidazole derivative containing pyrrolidine ring (**3f**) and 2,6-dimethyl benzimidazole derivative containing *N*-ethylpiperazine ring (**4e**) showed moderate activity against *B. subtilis*. 2,6-Dimethyl benzimidazole derivative containing piperazine ring (**4a**) and *N*-ethylpiperazine ring (**4e**) showed good activity against *K. pneumoniae*. 2-Methyl benzimidazole derivative containing *N*-ethylpiperazine ring (**3e**), diphenylamine ring (**3h**), 2,6-dimethyl benzimidazole derivative containing cyclopentyl ring (**5b**) showed moderate activity against *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae*. 2,6-Dimethyl benzimidazole derivative containing pyrrolidine ring (**4f**) showed excellent activity while

Table 1. Physical data of synthesized compounds

Compd.	Molecular formula	Molecular weight (g)	Yield (%)	m.p. (°C)	R_f value ^a	N (%)	
						Calcd.	Found
3a	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ N ₄	230.31	72	123–125	0.52	24.33	24.20
3b	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ O	231.29	74	152–153	0.37	18.17	18.09
3c	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ N ₃	229.32	74	135–137	0.48	18.32	18.27
3d	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ N ₄	244.34	70	161–162	0.56	22.93	22.94
3e	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ N ₄	258.36	75	166–168	0.50	21.69	21.62
3f	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ N ₃	215.29	72	157–158	0.43	19.52	19.45
3g	C ₁₃ H ₁₉ N ₃	217.31	76	122–124	0.53	19.34	19.29
3h	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₃	313.40	72	165–167	0.47	13.41	13.33
4a	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ N ₄	244.34	68	178–180	0.68	22.93	22.84
4b	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ N ₃ O	245.32	70	153–155	0.55	17.13	17.08
4c	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₃	243.35	73	170–171	0.60	17.27	17.16
4d	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ N ₄	258.36	74	158–160	0.63	21.69	21.58
4e	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ N ₄	272.39	78	132–134	0.58	20.57	20.41
4f	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ N ₃	229.32	74	138–140	0.64	18.32	18.27
4g	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ N ₃	231.34	64	145–147	0.46	18.16	18.12
4h	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₃	327.42	68	176–178	0.48	12.83	12.57
5a	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₂	200.28	80	158–160	0.55	13.99	13.79
5b	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ N ₃	214.31	82	185–187	0.65	13.07	12.95

^aSolvent used for TLC is chloroform : methanol (9 : 1).**Table 2.** Antibacterial activity of test compounds (100 µg/mL) and Clotrimazole (100 µg/mL)

Compd.	Zone of inhibition in mm ±SD			
	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>
Control	–	–	–	–
Ciprofloxacin	20.0 ± 0.89	21.0 ± 0.87	27.0 ± 0.45	19.0 ± 0.57
3a	12.0 ± 0.57	7.0 ± 0.76	8.0 ± 0.50	7.0 ± 0.50
3b	8.0 ± 0.50	7.5 ± 0.76	8.5 ± 0.87	9.5 ± 0.57
3c	6.5 ± 0.60	7.5 ± 0.57	9.0 ± 0.50	8.0 ± 0.76
3d	8.5 ± 0.50	8.0 ± 0.76	9.0 ± 0.89	7.5 ± 1.20
3e	7.0 ± 0.50	8.0 ± 0.89	11.0 ± 0.89	10.0 ± 0.50
3f	11.0 ± 0.76	11.0 ± 0.98	7.0 ± 0.50	7.5 ± 0.76
3g	6.5 ± 0.87	6.0 ± 0.65	12.0 ± 0.56	13.0 ± 0.76
3h	8.0 ± 0.95	9.5 ± 0.78	11.0 ± 1.3	8.0 ± 0.56
4a	9.0 ± 0.76	8.0 ± 0.50	10.0 ± 0.50	12.5 ± 0.50
4b	6.5 ± 0.50	6.5 ± 0.76	7.5 ± 0.76	9.0 ± 0.87
4c	10.0 ± 0.57	7.0 ± 0.76	6.5 ± 0.50	7.0 ± 0.98
4d	7.5 ± 0.65	6.5 ± 0.87	7.0 ± 0.98	8.5 ± 1.00
4e	10.0 ± 0.87	7.0 ± 0.50	6.5 ± 0.67	11.0 ± 0.56
4f	13.0 ± 0.50	8.0 ± 1.10	6.5 ± 0.76	7.0 ± 0.76
4g	8.5 ± 0.45	8.0 ± 0.56	8.0 ± 0.50	7.5 ± 0.89
4h	8.0 ± 0.78	7.5 ± 0.98	8.5 ± 1.30	8.0 ± 0.76
5a	12.5 ± 0.50	9.0 ± 0.67	7.0 ± 0.50	7.5 ± 0.45
5b	7.0 ± 0.56	9.0 ± 0.78	11.0 ± 0.45	8.5 ± 0.50

Table 3. Antifungal activity of tested compounds (100 µg/mL) and Clotrimazole (100 µg/mL)

Compd.	Zone of inhibition in mm ±SD	
	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>A. tubingensis</i>
Control	–	–
Clotrimazole	18.0 ± 0.57	19.0 ± 0.76
3a	8.0 ± 0.76	7.0 ± 0.56
3b	7.5 ± 0.89	8.0 ± 0.67
3c	7.5 ± 0.67	8.0 ± 0.98
3d	7.0 ± 0.98	7.0 ± 0.89
3e	7.0 ± 1.00	11.0 ± 0.76
3f	8.5 ± 0.50	7.0 ± 0.50
3g	7.5 ± 0.67	8.0 ± 0.45
3h	9.5 ± 0.50	7.5 ± 0.76
4a	7.0 ± 0.76	8.0 ± 0.89
4b	11.0 ± 0.89	6.5 ± 1.10
4c	10.0 ± 0.98	8.5 ± 0.50
4d	8.5 ± 0.45	9.0 ± 0.76
4e	9.5 ± 0.56	6.5 ± 0.45
4f	18.5 ± 0.76	8.0 ± 1.20
4g	10.0 ± 0.87	11.5 ± 0.56
4h	9.0 ± 0.98	9.5 ± 0.76
5a	6.5 ± 0.50	13.0 ± 1.00
5b	7.0 ± 0.45	8.5 ± 0.50

morpholine ring (**4b**) showed moderate activity against *C. albicans*. 2-Methyl benzimidazole derivative containing cyclopentyl ring (**5a**) showed good activity while *N*-ethylpiperazine ring (**3e**) and 2,6-dimethyl benzimidazole derivative containing diethylamine ring showed moderate activity against *A. tubingensis* (Tables 2 and 3).

Analgesic activity :

Acetic acid induced writhing model in mice was used for the screening of synthesized compounds. All compounds showed potent analgesic activity. Among all compounds 2,6-dimethyl-1-(piperazin-1-ylmethyl)-1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazole (**4a**) showed excellent analgesic activity (81%, 100 mg/kg b.w.). While **3c**, **3e** and **4e** have been also shown good activity. It was viewed that for structure activity relationship (SAR), the introduction of piperazine, piperidine, *N*-ethylpiperazine ring in 2-me-

Table 4. Analgesic activity of tested compounds (100 mg/kg b.w.) and Diclofenac sodium (25 mg/kg b.w.)

Compounds	Mean writhing ±SEM	% Protection
Control	70.0 ± 0.73	–
Diclofenac sodium	17.0 ± 0.37	75.71
3a	19.3 ± 0.21	72.43
3b	22.3 ± 0.56	68.14
3c	15.0 ± 0.36	78.57
3d	30.0 ± 0.73	57.14
3e	16.3 ± 0.56	76.71
3f	21.7 ± 0.56	69.04
3g	27.3 ± 0.21	61.00
3h	27.0 ± 0.37	61.43
4a	13.3 ± 0.56	81.00
4b	24.3 ± 0.56	65.29
4c	28.7 ± 0.76	59.04
4d	18.3 ± 0.56	73.86
4e	14.7 ± 0.21	79.04
4f	24.0 ± 0.37	65.71
4g	20.0 ± 0.21	71.43
4h	22.7 ± 0.21	67.61
5a	19.0 ± 0.37	72.86
5b	28.0 ± 0.37	60.00

Data represent mean values ±SEM of six mice per group.

Data were analyzed using one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's test $p < 0.01$.

thyl and 2,6-dimethyl benzimidazole increased the analgesic activity (Table 4).

Anti-inflammatory :

For anti-inflammatory activity, carrageenan induced paw oedema model in wistar albino rats were used for screening of synthesized compounds. Diclofenac (25 mg/kg b.w.) was served as standard drug for comparison. Most compounds showed good activity but 2-methyl-1-(piperidin-1-ylmethyl)-1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazole (**3c**) showed promising anti-inflammatory activity with 100 mg/kg b.w. while **3d**, **3f**, **4c**, **4f** have also shown good activity. For SAR, the introduction of *N*-methylpiperazine, piperidine, pyrrolidine ring in 2-methyl and 2,6-dimethyl benzimidazole increased the anti-inflammatory activity (Table 5).

Table 5. Anti-inflammatory activity of tested compounds (100 mg/kg b.w.) and Diclofenac sodium (25 mg/kg b.w.)

Compd.	Paw oedema volume							
	After 30 min		After 1 h		After 2 h		After 3h	
	Mean	% OI	Mean	% OI	Mean	% OI	Mean	% OI
Control	0.57 ± 0.02	–	0.67 ± 0.00	–	0.56 ± 0.03	–	0.42 ± 0.02	–
Diclofenac	0.35 ± 0.00	38.60	0.37 ± 0.01	44.78	0.21 ± 0.00	62.5	0.12 ± 0.01	71.42
3a	0.38 ± 0.01	33.33	0.40 ± 0.00	40.29	0.24 ± 0.02	57.14	0.15 ± 0.02	64.29
3b	0.37 ± 0.02	35.09	0.39 ± 0.01	41.79	0.23 ± 0.03	58.93	0.14 ± 0.03	66.67
3c	0.33 ± 0.04	42.10	0.35 ± 0.00	47.76	0.18 ± 0.01	67.86	0.09 ± 0.00	78.57
3d	0.35 ± 0.00	38.60	0.37 ± 0.02	44.78	0.22 ± 0.00	60.71	0.12 ± 0.02	71.42
3e	0.36 ± 0.01	36.84	0.37 ± 0.03	44.78	0.23 ± 0.00	58.93	0.13 ± 0.05	69.05
3f	0.33 ± 0.04	42.10	0.34 ± 0.04	49.25	0.18 ± 0.05	67.86	0.10 ± 0.01	76.19
3g	0.36 ± 0.03	36.84	0.39 ± 0.01	41.79	0.22 ± 0.03	60.71	0.14 ± 0.08	66.67
3h	0.37 ± 0.02	35.09	0.39 ± 0.00	41.79	0.23 ± 0.00	58.93	0.14 ± 0.03	66.67
4a	0.34 ± 0.01	40.35	0.38 ± 0.00	43.28	0.20 ± 0.03	64.29	0.13 ± 0.01	69.05
4b	0.37 ± 0.00	35.09	0.41 ± 0.01	38.8	0.23 ± 0.01	58.93	0.14 ± 0.00	66.67
4c	0.32 ± 0.00	43.86	0.36 ± 0.04	46.27	0.19 ± 0.02	66.07	0.10 ± 0.02	76.19
4d	0.35 ± 0.01	38.61	0.37 ± 0.02	44.78	0.21 ± 0.01	62.5	0.12 ± 0.04	71.42
4e	0.37 ± 0.02	35.09	0.38 ± 0.00	43.28	0.24 ± 0.00	57.14	0.13 ± 0.03	69.05
4f	0.32 ± 0.00	43.86	0.35 ± 0.05	47.76	0.20 ± 0.03	64.29	0.10 ± 0.00	76.19
4g	0.38 ± 0.01	33.33	0.40 ± 0.01	40.29	0.22 ± 0.07	60.70	0.14 ± 0.01	66.67
4h	0.37 ± 0.01	35.09	0.38 ± 0.02	43.28	0.23 ± 0.02	58.93	0.13 ± 0.03	69.05
5a	0.38 ± 0.00	33.33	0.40 ± 0.00	40.29	0.25 ± 0.01	55.36	0.17 ± 0.01	59.52
5b	0.36 ± 0.01	36.84	0.38 ± 0.01	43.28	0.23 ± 0.03	58.93	0.13 ± 0.00	69.05

Data represent mean values ± SEM of six rats per group.

Data were analyzed using one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's test $p < 0.01$.

Conclusion

According to the data which is reported in the table, it was concluded that Mannich bases of 2-methyl and 2,6-dimethyl benzimidazole were synthesized in good yield. Most of the compounds showed antimicrobial, analgesic and anti-inflammatory activity. Compound **3a**, **4a**, **5a** showed good antibacterial and **4f**, **4g** showed good anti-fungal activity. Compound **4a** showed highest analgesic while **3c** showed highest anti-inflammatory activity.

These derivatives are the subject of many research studies due to their widespread potential biological activities. It is noticed that addition of groups on 2, 3, 5 and 6 position of benzimidazole gives potent therapeutic compounds. So, it is concluded that benzimidazole derivatives impact on chemists and biochemists for further search of analgesic and anti-inflammatory agents containing Mannich bases.

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